

Church of St. George and St. Nicholas, Anydri

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The double church of St. George and St. Nicholas, located in the village of Anydri, overlooks both the mountainous landscape of southern Crete and the sea beyond. Located at the top of the Anydri Gorge, the village is connected to the coast via a 3km trail. Dating to 1323, the church of St. George, the original structure on the site, was painted by Ioannis Pagomenos. A single nave barrel vaulted construction, the church of St. George includes a high central transept which draws the eye upwards as one reaches the center of the nave. This architectural type is unusual in Crete. By contrast, the connected church of St. Nicholas, dated by stylistic analysis to the middle of the fourteenth century, is a barrel-vaulted structure that was later extended to the west. Three archways, two in the nave and one in the sanctuary, connect the northern wall of the church of St. Nicholas to the southern wall of the church of St. George. Each sanctuary is separated from the nave by a modern wooden iconostasis. In the church of St. George, the apse of the sanctuary includes an image of the Deesis where the figure of St. George takes the place of St. John the Baptist. The lower register of the apse includes four co-officiating bishops flanking the Melismos. As traditional, the Hospitality of Abraham and the Annunciation are presented on the triumphal arch around the main altar. The northern wall of the sanctuary includes a niche decorated with Saints Polycarpus and John Eleëmon with the image of St. Stephen to the right of the niche. The southern niche of the sanctuary was removed to create the archway leading to the church of St. Nicholas. From this only the image of St. Romanus remains. Outside the sanctuary, the transept vault includes scenes from the Christological cycle including the Raising of Lazarus and the Presentation of the Temple. Much of the southern wall has been lost due to the opening of the second archway, however, the northern wall includes a large figure of St. George on horseback killing the dragon. Scenes from the life of St. George, including his martyrdom on the wheel, fill the vault of the western part of the church. Below these scenes on the northern wall is a large image of St. Demetrios on horseback. He is flanked by the images of St. Marina and St. Anastasia. As the southern wall was damaged by the archway leading to the church of St. Nicholas, only the images of St. Sophia and another unidentified female saint remain. Likewise, the western wall only preserves the images of St. Kyriaki, to the left of the entrance, and St. Paraskevi, to the right. The dedicatory inscription, located above the image of St. Sophia and giving the date of 10 May 6831 (1323), indicates that almost everyone in the village contributed to the creation of this church. The Church of St. Nicholas can be tentatively dated to the middle of the fourteenth century based on stylistic analysis of the remaining paintings of which most are in a poor state of preservation. The apse is decorated with an image of St. Nicholas flanked by Christ and the Virgin while the southern wall of the sanctuary includes images of St. John Chrysostom and St. Cyril of Crete. The barrel vault is also badly damaged but the scene of the Ascension along with a handful of scenes from the life of St. Nicholas can be identified. The nave of the church includes scenes from the Last Judgment including the Apostle Tribunal, a Choir of Saints, and a Choir of Apostles. Nothing else remains of the paintings on the northern or western walls of the church.

Date Range: 1323 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Village of Anydri, Selino, Crete

Region tags: Greece, Crete

The village of Anydri is located on the southern coast of Crete, just east of Palaiochora at an elevation of roughly 200m. Situated at the top of the Anydri Gorge, the village is connected to the coast via a 3km

trail.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. See no. 21, 63-66 (with earlier bibliography)
- Source 2: Bissinger, Manfred. Kreta. Byzantinische Wandmalerei. Münchener Arbeiten Zur Kunstgeschichte Und Archäologie 4. Munich: Editio Maris, 1995. See no. 53
- Source 3: Lassithiotakis, K. "Εκκλησίες της Δυτικής Κρήτης. Δ. Επαρχία Σελίνου, αριθ. 57-100." Κρητικά Χρονικά 22 (1970): 166-70. See p. 176

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Terracing
- Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: Both of the connected churches are single nave barrel vaulted structures, however the earlier church, the church of St. George, includes a high central transept. The church is surrounded by a modern cemetery.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: Worship and burial.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to St. George and St. Nicholas.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Both St. George and St. Nicholas.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Other [specify]: Per the dedicatory inscription, the church was built by members of the surrounding community.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– I don't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: plaster and stone

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– No

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings include images of Christ in the Deesis and in the Christological cycle.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings include standing figures of saints, monks and prophets. It also includes scenes from the lives of St. George and St. Nicholas.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icons are included in the wooden iconostasis.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

Notes: The painting cycle reflects standard iconography of the Orthodox Christian faith.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Beyond the dedicatory inscription, there are inscriptions identifying the figures.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: There is a formal dedication for the northern church of St. George on the southern wall.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: A contemporary cemetery surrounds the church.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– No

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

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